

Questionnaire to be responded by the Participants

4 respostas

Profile of Participants (reusing question 4 of the " Beyond Code Generation: An Observational Study of ChatGPT Usage in Software Engineering Practice" Exit Survey)

What is your level of experience in ChatGPT?

 Copiar

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What is your level of expertise in the NFR Framework?

 Copiar

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What is your level of expertise in Transparency?

4 respostas

Quantitative Evaluation (reusing questions 5, 7, 8, 13, and 14 from "Beyond Code Generation: An Observational Study of ChatGPT Usage in Software Engineering Practice" Exit Survey)

Did ChatGPT provide helpful responses to your questioning?

4 respostas

How did you perceive ChatGPT level of understandability for your questioning?

4 respostas

What is the level of Trust you would assign to ChatGPT based on its answers to questioning?

4 respostas

How helpful was the interaction with ChatGPT?

 Copiar

4 respostas

After using ChatGPT for this research, what are the potential you see in using it for further research?

 Copiar

4 respostas

Qualitative Evaluation (inspired by questions 10 and 11 from "Beyond Code Generation: An Observational Study of ChatGPT Usage in Software Engineering Practice" Exit Survey)

Write a summary of your experience focusing on consistency and on what you have learned

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ChatGPT requires proper contextualization and clear instructions on the desired output. At first glance, it appears to deliver logical and coherent results. However, its lack of transparency regarding the sources it uses already raises some concerns. Moreover, when tasked with NLP activities—such as identifying qualities and their interrelations within texts it has generated—

the outcomes tend to vary with each execution. I've observed different responses when switching accounts, asking to print results in the same chat, or uploading a file containing the text. This inconsistency not only undermines confidence but also suggests that the time spent querying this "oracle" might be better invested in a manual process that offers more reliability.

The responses obtained from GPT were enriching as they adequately considered the context I provided. The answers were direct and highly explanatory regarding the discussed concepts, presenting few inconsistencies throughout the chat. There were no hallucinations or performance issues.

Since the questions were predefined and not modified based on the responses, some earlier answers already encompassed the responses to later questions. However, this exercise was interesting for assessing the possibility of greater detail or inconsistencies between responses. Thus, the SIG proposed at the end of the chat is not the sum of all aspects raised during the questions but it represents the main and frequently mentioned points.

Given the level of explainability demonstrated in GPT's responses regarding softgoals in the context of Transparency, I consider that the information gathered contributes to the understanding of the field and allows a Requirements Engineer to analyze its applicability.

GPT's responses included suggestions for the addition, removal, renaming, merging, and repositioning of certain softgoals, as well as the introduction of new correlations. Some examples of suggestions include: adding Timeliness (help Informativeness) and Explainability (help Understandability); renaming Validity to Compliance (help Auditability); merging Composability and Decomposability into Modularity; modifying contributions such that Performability helps Accessibility (instead of Performability helping Usability) and Dependability helps Informativeness (instead of Dependability helping Understandability); and removing Comparable, as it may have lesser importance compared to the other softgoals. However, there are many other suggestions in the responses, which may be irrelevant or even incorrect, requiring time and effort for proper analysis.

ChatGPT gave quick answers with a lot of information about my questions. Despite the detailed explanations, ChatGPT did not demonstrate continuous coherence in the answers. It changed the content many times despite the question being the same. In research, we need a deep analysis of the information obtained. The chat helps to provide a vast set of general information quickly. Then, it must be analyzed to fix or enrich information.

ChatGPT's main function is to provide information and quick analyses of text that may be worked to organize it better or evaluated to provide better information.

The interview with GPT aimed at eliciting its knowledge on the topic of transparency, with interactions providing context. This context was given by asking about its perception on how the qualities of accessibility, usability, informativeness, understandability, and auditability relate to the concept of transparency. GPT shows a level of understanding of the concept transparency but missed important aspects. First, due to its misinterpretation of accessibility and mixing it with usability, second due to the merge of auditability with accountability, which are different concepts, third using openness as a quality related to transparency, whereas its

detail is far from the concept of openness itself, and by bringing a concept/name that is often used as a synonym of transparency. Second, it failed in providing a consistent conceptual model, since it uses operationalizations in place of qualities for assigning detail to the four main qualities (for instance "visual aids", "documentation",...). It is also a case that the model does not follow the principle of modularity, as it uses an AND relation in a naming one of the four qualities.

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